

Synthesis of several 2-(5-chloro-3-methyl-1-(pyridin-2-yl) pyrazolidin-4-yl)-3-substitutedphenylthiazolidin-4-ones as prospective antimicrobial agents

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ABSTRACT

Several 2-(5-chloro-3-methyl-1-(pyridin-2-yl) pyrazolidin-4-yl)-3- substitutedphenylthiazolidin-4-one (4a-f) have been synthesized by conventional synthesis methodology. The synthesized derivatives were characterized by IR, ¹H-NMR, Mass and elemental analysis (C, H, N) . Furthermore the synthesized 2-(5-chloro-3-methyl-1-(pyridin-2-yl) pyrazolidin-4-yl)-3-substitutedphenylthiazolidin-4-one (4a-f) were tested for antimicrobial activities. The compound 4c displayed significant biological activities among the all tested derivatives.

Keywords: Antibacterial, antifungal, thiazolidin-4-one, acute toxicity.

INTRODUCTION

Pyrazole symbolizes a class of simple aromatic ring organic compounds of the heterocyclic series which is a 5-membered ring skeleton composed of three carbon and two nitrogen atoms. Ludwig Knorr was the first who coined the term pyrazole in 1883. In 1959, the first natural pyrazole, 1-pyrazolyl-alanine, was isolated from seeds of watermelons [1-2]. A bulk of literature is available to show the biological versatility such as anti-inflammatory [3], antibacterial [4-5], anti-convulsant [6], anticancer [7-8], anti-depressant [9], anti-hyperglycemic [10], antiviral [11], antipyretic [12], antioxidant [13], antitubercular [14], fungicides [15], and analgesic activities [16]. These pyrazoles have also found applications in transition-metal chemistry as an analytical reagent [17]. On the other hand, thiazolidinone bearing derivatives have been known to exhibit a wide range of physiological and pharmacological activities [18-23]. Above observation encouraged us to design several pyrazole bearing thiazolidinones with the hope to show significant antibacterial and antifungal activity with lesser amount of toxicity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chemistry

Ethyl acetoacetate and 2-hydrazinylpyridine undergo cyclo-condensation reaction to furnish 3-methyl- 1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5 (4H)-one (1) which on chloroformylated yielded 5-chloro-3-methyl- 1-phenyl -1H-pyrazole -4-carbaldehyde (2). Compound 2 on reaction with different 5-substituted anilines furnished 2-[[5-chloro -3-methyl- 1-(pyridin-2-yl) pyrazolidin -4-yl] methylene] substituted anilines (3a-f). Cyclisation of compounds 3a-f was carried out by means of thioglycolic acid to produce 2-[[5-chloro-3- methyl-1-(pyridin-2-yl) pyrazolidin -4- yl] -3- substitute dphenylthiazolidin -4- ones (4a-f) (Scheme-1). Synthesised derivatives were assayed using the cup plate method for antimicrobial activity against selected pathogenic panel of microbes. The screening results were compared with standard ampicillin trihydrate and fluconazole respectively for antibacterial and antifungal testing. Furthermore the most potent congener was also tested for lethal dose. From the antimicrobial screening data of compounds 3 and 4a-f, it was found that conversion of compound 3a-f into thiazolidinone derivatives i.e. 4a-f, brought enhancing antibacterial and antifungal activity. Among the derivatives 4a-f, derivative 4c

and 4e showed remarkable potency against the used pathogens. On the other hand, remaining compounds exhibited mild to moderate activity. Results revealed that compound 4c was

found the most potent one, showing broad spectrum inhibitory profile having lesser toxicity (Table-1).

Scheme-1

Comp. no.	Antibacterial inhibition (mm)				Antifungal inhibition (mm)			
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. Coli</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>	<i>A. fumigatus</i>	<i>C. glabrata</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>C. krusei</i>
4a	5	-	-	5	-	-	-	-
4b	10	5	5	8	5	-	-	5
4c	16	18	20	18	12	10	8	10
4d	12	5	10	10	6	-	-	10
4e	10	10	15	8	10	-	5	6
4f	5	10	10	10	10	-	5	8
Ampicillin trihydrate (std.)	16	20	20	20	-	-	-	-
Fluconazole (std.)	-	-	-	-	20	15	16	15
DMF (control)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

-: showing no activity

Table-1. Antibacterial and antifungal data for the synthesized compounds (4a-f).

Antimicrobial test

All the newly synthesized compounds were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activity. All the bacterial and fungal strains were clinical isolates, identified with conventional morphological and biochemical methods. Microorganisms employed antibacterial studies were *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klasiella pneumonia* and *Proteus vulgaris*. Disk diffusion method [24-25] was used for determination of the preliminary antibacterial activity. Disks measuring 6.25 mm in diameter were punched from Whatman no. 1 filter paper. Batches of 100 disks were dispensed to each screw-capped bottle and sterilized by dry heat at 140 °C for an h. The test compounds were prepared with different concentrations using DMF. One milliliter containing 100 times the amount of chemical in each disk was added to each bottle, which contained 100 disks. Disks of each concentration were for placed in triplicate in nutrient agar medium seeded with fresh bacteria separately. The incubation was carried out at 37 °C for 24 h. Ampicillin trihydrate was used as a standard drug. Solvent and growth controls were kept and zones of inhibition were noted. The inhibition zone values of the tested compounds against the tested bacteria strains summarized in Table 1. On the other hand, the newly prepared compounds were screened for their in vitro antifungal activity against *Aspergillus fumigates* (plant isolate), *Candida glabrata*, *Candida albicans* and *Candida krusei* in DMSO by the serial plate dilution method [26-27]. Fluconazole (antifungal) was used as reference drug. Sabouraud's agar media were prepared by dissolving peptone (1 g), D-glucose (4 g), and agar (2 g) in distilled water (100 ml) and adjusting the pH to 5.7. Normal saline was used to make a suspension of the spore of fungal strain for lawning. A loopful of particular fungal strain was transferred to 3 ml saline to get a suspension of the corresponding species. Agar media (20 ml) was poured into each petri dish. Excess suspension was decanted and the plates were dried by placing in an incubator at 37 °C for 1 h. Using an agar punch wells were made into each well labeled. A control was also prepared in triplicate and maintained at 37 °C for 3-4 days. Antifungal activity was determined by measuring the diameter of the inhibition zone. The inhibitory data of the tested compounds against the tested fungal strains were recorded in Table 1.

Acute toxicity test

Lethal dose [28] (LD50) of test compounds were determined in albino mice. After 24 h of drug administration, percent mortality in each group was observed from the data obtained LD50. Data revealed that compound 4c does not show any toxicity up to dose of 12.56 mg/ml body weight in mice.

Experimental Material

All the chemicals used for the preparation of desired derivatives, were obtained from Sisco Research Laboratories (SRL), Mumbai, India; Qualigen Fine Chemicals, Mumbai, India; E. Merck Ltd., New Delhi, India. Reference drugs ampicillin trihydrate and fluconazole were procured from Ind-Swift Pharmaceutical, Panjab, India and Macleods Pharmaceutical, Mumbai, India respectively.

Measurement

The melting points of the compounds were determined in open glass capillaries with the help of thermonic melting points apparatus (Campbell Electronics, Mumbai, India) and are uncorrected. The homogeneity of all the newly synthesized compounds were routinely checked by TLC on silica gel G plates and spots were located by using iodine chamber. Elemental analysis was performed in Heraeus CHN rapid analyser. The results were found within the $\pm 0.4\%$ of theoretical values. Infrared spectra were recorded on KBr pellets on a Perkin Elmer system 2000 FTIR spectrometer and ¹H-NMR spectra on Bruker DPX 200 using TMS as internal standard.

Synthesis

Preparation of 3-Methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5(4H)-one (1)

An ethanolic solution of the ethyl acetoacetate (0.001 mol) and 2-hydrazinylpyridine (0.001 mol) was stirred at room temperature for 1 hr. The resulting reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 h. On completion of reaction, the reaction mixture was allowed to cool in ice bath to precipitate the solid. The solid filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol to give compound 1. Yield: 77%, R_f: 0.68. m.p. 127–129 °C. Anal. Calcd. For C₉H₁₁N₃O: C, 61.00; H, 6.26; N, 23.71%. Found: C, 60.91; H, 6.25; N, 23.76%. IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3170, 3140, 2960, 1680, 1611, 1572, 1280, 1231. ¹H-NMR (DMSO-*d*₆ /ppm): 6.86-7.20 (m, 4H), 6.14 (brs, 1H), 5.20 (s, 1H), 4.45 (d, 2H, CH₂), 1.12 (s, 3H). MS (m/z): 177.09 (M)⁺.

Preparation of 5-Chloro-3-methyl-1-phenyl -1H-pyrazole -4-carbaldehyde (2)

Dimethylformamide solution of compound 1 (0.001 mol) cooled and followed by the dropwise addition of phosphorus oxychloride (0.002 mol). After completion of the addition the resulting mixture was refluxed for 2 h. On completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was cooled, poured into crushed ice-water, filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol to furnish yellowish brown solid compound 2. Yield: 75%, m.p. 142–144 °C. Anal. Calcd. For C₁₀H₁₂N₃OCl: C, 53.22; H, 5.36; N, 18.62%. Found: C, 53.29; H, 5.37; N, 18.60%. IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3162, 3146, 2964, 1688, 1620, 1565, 1277, 1237. ¹H-NMR (DMSO-*d*₆ /ppm): 9.70 (s, 1H), 6.80-7.15 (m, 4H), 6.10 (brs, 1H), 5.33 (dd, 1H), 4.58 (d, 1H), 4.15 (d, 1H), 1.03 (s, 3H). MS (m/z): 225.07 (M)⁺.

General preparation of 2-[[5-chloro-3-methyl-1-(pyridin-2-yl)pyrazolidin-4-yl]methylene]substituted anilines (3a-f)

An ethanolic mixture of compound 2 (0.001 mol) and substituted anilines (0.001 mol) in the presence of few drops of glacial acid was refluxed for 5-7 hr. On completion of the reaction, reaction mixture cooled, poured onto crushed ice-water, stirred, filtered, dried, recrystallized from suitable solvents to yield compounds 3a-f.

N-[[5-chloro-3-methyl-1-(pyridin-2-yl) pyrazolidin-4-yl] methylene] substituted aniline 3a.

Yield: 68%, m.p. 171–173 °C. Anal. Calcd. For C₁₆H₁₇N₄Cl: C, 63.89; H, 5.70; N, 18.63%. Found: C, 63.95; H, 5.67; N, 18.54%. IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3170 (NH), 3140 (C...H aromatic), 2963, 1678, 1616, 1568, 1283, 1227. ¹H-NMR (DMSO-*d*₆

/ppm): 8.60 (s, 1H), 6.68-7.31 (m, 9H), 6.00 (brs, 1H), 4.51-5.00 (m, 3H), 1.05 (s, 3H). MS (m/z): 300.79 (M)⁺.

N-[[5-chloro-3-methyl-1-(pyridin-2-yl)pyrazolidin-4-yl]methylene]-3-aminoaniline 3b.

Yield: 63%, m.p. 148–150 °C. Anal. Calcd. For C₁₆H₁₈N₅Cl: C, 60.85; H, 5.75; N, 22.18%. Found: C, 60.91; H, 5.74; N, 22.22%. IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3161, 3133, 2968, 1683, 1625, 1574, 1270, 1220. ¹H-NMR (DMSO-*d*₆/ppm): 8.71 (s, 1H), 6.70-7.35 (m, 8H), 6.15 (brs, 2H), 5.51 (brs, 1H), 4.60-4.94 (m 3H), 0.96 (s, 3H). MS (m/z): 315.80 (M)⁺.

N-[[5-chloro-3-methyl-1-(pyridin-2-yl)pyrazolidin-4-yl]methylene]-4-aminoaniline 3c.

Yield: 72%, m.p. 155–157 °C. Anal. Calcd. For C₁₆H₁₈N₅Cl: C, 60.85; H, 5.75; N, 22.18%. Found: C, 60.87; H, 5.77; N, 22.20%. IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3165, 3130, 2965, 1680, 1620, 1570, 1275, 1223. ¹H-NMR (DMSO-*d*₆/ppm): 8.65 (s, 1H), 6.74-7.37 (m, 8H), 6.20 (brs, 2H), 5.72 (brs, 1H), 4.71-5.17 (m 3H), 1.02 (s, 3H). MS (m/z): 315.80 (M)⁺.

N-[[5-chloro-3-methyl-1-(pyridin-2-yl)pyrazolidin-4-yl]methylene]-2-bromoaniline 3d.

Yield: 66%, m.p. 114–116 °C. Anal. Calcd. For C₁₆H₁₆N₄BrCl: C, 50.61; H, 4.25; N, 14.76%. Found: C, 50.66; H, 4.26; N, 14.80%. IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3157, 3128, 2958, 1676, 1613, 1565, 1268, 1217. ¹H-NMR (DMSO-*d*₆/ppm): 8.61 (s, 1H), 6.78-7.30 (m, 8H), 5.79 (brs, 1H), 4.74-5.13 (m 3H), 1.11 (s, 3H). MS (m/z): 380.02 (M)⁺.

N-[[5-chloro-3-methyl-1-(pyridin-2-yl)pyrazolidin-4-yl]methylene]-3-bromoaniline 3e.

Yield: 62%, m.p. 123–125 °C. Anal. Calcd. For C₁₆H₁₆N₄BrCl: C, 50.61; H, 4.25; N, 14.76%. Found: C, 50.64; H, 4.22; N, 14.85%. IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3160, 3123, 2961, 1679, 1616, 1568, 1270, 1220. ¹H-NMR (DMSO-*d*₆/ppm): 8.57 (s, 1H), 6.66-7.22 (m, 8H), 5.71 (brs, 1H), 4.80-5.16 (m 3H), 1.08 (s, 3H). MS (m/z): 380.02 (M)⁺.

N-[[5-chloro-3-methyl-1-(pyridin-2-yl)pyrazolidin-4-yl]methylene]-4-bromoaniline 3f.

Yield: 67%, m.p. 139–141 °C. Anal. Calcd. For C₁₆H₁₆N₄BrCl: C, 50.61; H, 4.25; N, 14.76%. Found: C, 50.60; H, 4.23; N, 14.80%. IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3159, 3126, 2963, 1680, 1614, 1562, 1265, 1215. ¹H-NMR (DMSO-*d*₆/ppm): 8.67 (s, 1H), 6.70-7.35 (m, 8H), 5.80 (brs, 1H), 4.68-5.10 (m 3H), 1.15 (s, 3H). MS (m/z): 380.02 (M)⁺.

General preparation of 2-[[5-chloro-3-methyl-1-(pyridin-2-yl)pyrazolidin-4-yl]-3-substitutedphenyl-thiazolidin-4-ones (4a-f)

A mixture of compound 3a-f (0.001 mol) in N,N'-dimethyl formamide and thioglycolic acid (0.001 mol) in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride was refluxed for 2-4 h. After completion of reaction (monitored by TLC), excess of solvent was distilled and cooled residual mass diluted with ice-water. The solid filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised by appropriate solvents to yield desired compounds 4a-f.

2-[[5-chloro-3-methyl-1-(pyridin-2-yl)pyrazolidin-4-yl]-3-phenylthiazolidin-4-ones 4a.

Yield: 67%, m.p. 139–141 °C. Anal. Calcd. For C₁₈H₁₉N₄ClSO: C, 57.67; H, 5.11; N, 14.94%. Found: C, 57.56; H, 5.16; N, 14.88%. IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3150, 3122, 2960, 1672, 1608, 1554, 1268, 1216, 667. ¹H-NMR (DMSO-*d*₆/ppm): 6.70-7.35 (m, 9H), 5.89 (brs, 1H), 4.35-4.80 (m 3H), 3.60 (s, 2H), 2.73 (s, 1H, CH), 1.00 (s, 3H). MS (m/z): 374.89 (M)⁺.

2-[[5-chloro-3-methyl-1-(pyridin-2-yl)pyrazolidin-4-yl]-3-aminophenylthiazolidin-4-ones 4b.

Yield: 55%, m.p. 167–169 °C. Anal. Calcd. For C₁₈H₂₀N₅ClSO: C, 55.45; H, 5.17; N, 17.96%. Found: C, 55.60; H, 5.15; N, 18.02%. IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3158, 3124, 2958, 1665, 1610, 1550, 1262, 1211, 669. ¹H-NMR (DMSO-*d*₆/ppm): 6.70-7.35 (m, 8H), 5.90 (brs, 1H), 5.22 (brs, 1H), 4.42-4.66 (m 3H), 3.58 (s, 2H), 2.65 (s, 1H), 1.08 (s, 3H). MS (m/z): 389.90 (M)⁺.

2-[[5-chloro-3-methyl-1-(pyridin-2-yl)pyrazolidin-4-yl]-4-aminophenylthiazolidin-4-ones 4c.

Yield: 60%, m.p. 183–185 °C. Anal. Calcd. For C₁₈H₂₀N₅ClSO: C, 55.45; H, 5.17; N, 17.96%. Found: C, 55.42; H, 5.19; N, 18.10%. IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3154, 3123, 2962, 1662, 1614, 1549, 1265, 1215, 663. ¹H-NMR (DMSO-*d*₆/ppm): 6.62-7.30 (m, 8H), 5.87 (brs, 1H), 5.24 (brs, 1H), 4.36-4.61 (m 3H), 3.62 (s, 2H), 2.69 (s, 1H), 1.04 (s, 3H). MS (m/z): 389.90 (M)⁺.

2-[[5-chloro-3-methyl-1-(pyridin-2-yl)pyrazolidin-4-yl]-2-bromophenylthiazolidin-4-ones 4d.

Yield: 51%, m.p. 128–130 °C. Anal. Calcd. For C₁₈H₁₈N₄ClBrSO: C, 47.64; H, 4.00; N, 12.35%. Found: C, 47.55; H, 4.03; N, 12.28%. IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3151, 3125, 2962, 1674, 1613, 1558, 1263, 1211, 658. ¹H-NMR (DMSO-*d*₆/ppm): 6.76-7.36 (m, 8H), 5.80 (brs, 1H), 4.30-4.82 (m 3H), 3.56 (s, 2H), 2.66 (s, 1H), 0.94 (s, 3H). MS (m/z): 453.78 (M)⁺.

2-[[5-chloro-3-methyl-1-(pyridin-2-yl)pyrazolidin-4-yl]-3-bromophenylthiazolidin-4-ones 4e.

Yield: 53%, m.p. 109–111 °C. Anal. Calcd. For C₁₈H₁₈N₄ClBrSO: C, 47.64; H, 4.00; N, 12.35%. Found: C, 47.60; H, 4.01; N, 12.35%. IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3157, 3120, 2960, 1679, 1610, 1551, 1258, 1217, 664. ¹H-NMR (DMSO-*d*₆/ppm): 6.67-7.29 (m, 8H), 5.75 (brs, 1H), 4.41-4.92 (m 3H), 3.46 (s, 2H), 2.79 (s, 1H), 1.12 (s, 3H). MS (m/z): 453.78 (M)⁺.

2-[[5-chloro-3-methyl-1-(pyridin-2-yl)pyrazolidin-4-yl]-4-bromophenylthiazolidin-4-ones 4f.

Yield: 48%, m.p. 148–150 °C. Anal. Calcd. For C₁₈H₁₈N₄ClBrSO: C, 47.64; H, 4.00; N, 12.35%. Found: C, 47.72; H, 3.96; N, 12.30%. IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3155, 3123, 2964, 1671, 1615, 1554, 1260, 1214, 661. ¹H-NMR (DMSO-*d*₆/ppm): 6.70-7.31 (m, 8H), 5.72 (brs, 1H), 4.45-4.93 (m 3H), 3.60 (s, 2H), 2.70 (s, 1H), 0.99 (s, 3H). MS (m/z): 453.78 (M)⁺.

CONCLUSION

In the present study, our attention was focused on the synthesis and antimicrobial evaluation of a series of 2-[[5-chloro-3-methyl-1-(pyridin-2-yl)pyrazolidin-4-yl]-3-sub

stitutedphenylthiazolidin-4-ones (4a-f). Based on the resulting biological evaluation data, compound 4c possessing 3-aminophenyl substitution; exhibited the most potent antimicrobial activity with lesser toxicity among all the synthesized thiazolidin-4-one derivatives of the series.

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